

Removal of chromium(VI) from aqueous solution using low cost adsorbent

N. K. Mishra

Chemistry Department, Bappa Sri Narain Vocational Post-Graduate College, Lucknow-226 001, India

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Column packed with tea leaves as adsorbent have been used for the removal of some toxic heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions. Breakthrough behaviour of Cr^{VI} on tea leaves has been studied. The effect of pH, concentration, flow rate on breakthrough capacity and effect of other diverse metal ions have been investigated. It has been observed that removal of Cr^{VI} is maximum at a pH value of 3.

There are reports on the removal of Cr^{VI} from aqueous solution using horticultural peat adsorbent¹, oat biomass agricultural by-products², cellose³, activated carbon⁴ etc. In the present study, a method has been developed to remove chromium(VI) using tea leaves (TL) and the optimum parameters have been investigated.

Results and discussion

The breakthrough behaviour of Cr^{VI} (5 ppm) as a function of pH has been studied. The uptake of Cr^{VI} decreases with the decreasing acidity of the solution. The adsorption of Cr^{VI} on tea leaves is almost nil at pH 4.0–6.0 and while at pH less than 4.0, significant adsorption of Cr^{VI} is observed. Optimum pH is 3.0 for maximum adsorption of Cr^{VI} on TL and further decrease in pH does not result any change in adsorption. Breakthrough capacity observed at pH 3.0 is 98.20 mg/5g-dry TL. This adsorption capacity of Cr^{VI} on TL can be explained mainly due to the presence of essential oil, caffeine, legumin and polyphenols in tea leaves.

The results of concentration effect of Cr^{VI} solution (pH ~3) reveal that the variation in concentration (5 to 50 ppm) has no significant effect on breakthrough capacity.

Flow rate was varied from 135 to 350 ml/h. It was found that breakthrough capacity remains almost same upto a flow rate of 250 ml/h. However, further increase in flow rate resulted in earlier breakthrough due to decreased contact time.

The results of recovery of Cr^{VI} in the presence of foreign metal ions Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} reveal that their presence does not cause only significant error. The removal of Cr^{VI} (10–50 mg) is quantitative in the presence of these metal ions (2 mg each) at pH ~3. This may be due to the fact that Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were washed away with 50 ml of HNO₃ (0.2 mol dm⁻³). The determination of Cr^{VI} was

carried out by standard procedure.

The breakthrough capacity of TL treated with 0.1 N NaOH is less than that of untreated TL. This decrease may be explained on the basis of the fact that probably legumin and polyphenols present in TL adsorb Cr^{VI} resulting higher breakthrough capacity. Cr^{VI} can be eluted from the exhausted column of tea leaves using 0.1 N NaOH as an eluent. However, the cost of adsorbent is minimal.

Experimental

Solutions of Cr^{VI} were prepared in tap-water using K₂Cr₂O₇ (B.D.H.). pH was adjusted with HCl. Presence of Cr^{VI} in the effluent was determined spectrophotometrically using diphenylcarbazide. The other chemical used were of AnalaR grade and used as such.

Locally available sieved sieve (60–100 mesh) TL was treated with water to remove the impurities. Then, water was filtered off and the tea leaves dried.

Breakthrough capacity of Cr^{VI} was determined by passing solution (pH ~3) through a glass column (30 cm × 1.2 cm i.d.) packed with dry TL (5 g). The flow rate was maintained at 135 ml/h.

Sample solutions containing Cr^{VI} (10–50 mg) and foreign metal ions Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (2 mg each) were prepared. The solution was passed through the column at a flow rate ~1 ml/min. Cr^{VI} was eluted with 40 ml of 0.25% diphenylcarbazide in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄.

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